

It was found that gallium(III)—DHP complex was more stable than gallium(III)—AHP complex. The above finding was in accordance with the class 'a' acceptor nature of Ga^{III} for which it forms stronger bond with an oxygen donor ligand than that with a nitrogen donor ligand. Of the two ligands DHP and AHP, the former could provide ($\bar{O}$, O) bonding and the latter bidentate ($\bar{O}$, N) to Ga^{III}, and hence the stability order DHP > AHP for Ga^{III} complexes.

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**Role of Excess Amount of Secondary Ligand L on Stability of some Heterochelates :
Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) + Iminodiacetic Acid (IMDA) + Biologically Important Amino Acids (L)**

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VARIOUS mixed ligand complexes with IMDA as the primary ligand have been studied¹. Bhattacharya *et al.*^{2,3} have investigated the mixed ligand system (MAL) involving bivalent metal ions like Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and histidine, iminodiacetic acid or nitrilotriacetic acid as primary ligand and polyhydroxyphenols or amino acids as secondary ligands.

In the present study, attempt have been made to study the formation constants of the title systems in presence of excess amount of secondary ligand L using modified form of Irving—Rossotti⁴ titration technique.

IMDA is known to form 1 : 1 complex with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} at pH ~6 and ~6.5, respectively, and is stable at higher pH, where the combination of secondary ligand starts⁵. The reaction can be shown as

$$K_{MAL}^{MA} = \frac{[MAL]}{[MA][L]}$$

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. quality. Metal perchlorates of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were prepared from their respective carbonates and their metal content determined. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of all the solutions. The experimental set-up and calculations described by Bhattacharya *et al.* were employed. The measurements were carried out at 30°.

The nature of the potentiometric curves was interpreted as done in earlier publications⁶. In the secondary ligand curve two equivalent extra acid was added in order to account for the extra-hydrogen ions liberated due to the combination of primary ligand IMDA. $\bar{n}$ and pL was calculated using same equation as done earlier⁶. Precise values of K_{MAL}^{MA} were obtained by using the method of averages⁷. The values are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

The order of the formation constants of the ternary complexes in presence of excess amount of secondary ligand L is the same as for the binary complexes^{8,9}. However the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} with excess amount of L significantly lower than K_{ML}^M and K_{MAL}^{ML} of binary complexes but slightly lower than K_{MAL}^{MA} (where M—A—L ratio is 1 : 1 : 1).

TABLE 1—MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF Zn^{II} AND Cd^{II}

Ionic strength = 0.2 M, Temp. = 30°

Ligand (L)	log $K_{Zn.L_2}^{Zn}$	log $K_{Zn.L}^{Zn.L}$	log $K_{Zn.A.L}^{Zn.A}$			log $K_{Cd.L}^{Cd}$	log $K_{Cd.L_2}^{Cd.L}$	log $K_{Cd.A.L}^{Cd.A}$		
			(1 : 1 : 1)	(1 : 1 : 1.5)	(1 : 1 : 2.5)			(1 : 1 : 1)	(1 : 1 : 1.5)	(1 : 1 : 2.5)
Glycine	5.22	4.37	4.11	4.07	4.01	4.22	3.69	3.55	3.46	3.40
α -Alanine	5.17	4.10	3.84	3.78	3.70	4.27	3.46	3.40	3.32	3.25
Leucine	4.74	4.36	3.54	3.47	3.41	3.92	3.56	3.00	2.97	2.90
iso-Leucine	4.88	4.33	3.58	3.50	3.42	3.94	3.37	3.00	2.95	2.89
Valine	4.74	4.24	3.50	3.42	3.34	3.91	3.22	3.02	2.98	2.92
Serine	5.06	4.11	4.00	3.93	3.82	3.95	3.80	3.05	3.02	2.95
Threonine	5.16	4.19	4.08	3.98	3.90	4.02	3.20	3.25	3.18	3.05
Methionine	4.69	3.96	3.59	3.49	3.38	4.04	3.15	3.20	3.15	3.02

* Values taken from literature for comparison. log $K_{MAL}^{MA} = \pm 0.05$ variation.

This can be explained by considering that the electrostatic repulsion between the primary ligand iminodiacetic acid and the secondary ligand amino acid is more. Iminodiacetic acid bearing two negative charges, therefore, the coordinating tendency of secondary ligand L to combine with [M(IMDA)] decreases significantly. Therefore, mixed ligand formation constant values are significantly lower than $K_{ML_1}^M$ and lower than $K_{ML_2}^{ML_1}$. The higher concentration of L is lowering the values of mixed ligand formation constants K_{MAL}^{MA} . Besides the charge repulsion, other factors may also affect the mixed ligand formation constant K_{MAL}^{MA} .

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Thermodynamic Functions of Biological Molecules. Pyrimidine and some of its Haloderivatives

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VIBRATIONAL analysis of pyrimidines have been studied by various workers¹⁻⁶. Allenstein *et al.*⁷ have studied 2-halopyrimidines and reported all the fundamental frequencies of 2-chloropyrimidine. 2,4,6-Trihalopyrimidines have also been studied by Kizuki *et al.*⁸ and Bailey and Steele^{9,10}. Although the vibrational analysis of these molecules have been studied, the thermodynamic functions of these molecules are not reported. With this end in view, we decided to compute the thermodynamic functions, namely, heat capacity (C_p°), enthalpy function ($H^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T , free energy function ($G^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T and entropy (S°) for these molecules at a pressure of 1 atm in the temperature range 100–1500 K under the rigid rotor-harmonic oscillator approximation and using the fundamental frequencies available in the literature^{7,9-11}.

Computation of thermodynamic properties: Once the vibrational frequencies of a molecule are known, it is possible to calculate the contribution of the vibrational energy to the total energy possessed by a molecule. In the same way, the rotational energy contribution can be calculated if the moments of inertia of the molecule are known. Thus, the spectroscopically measured frequencies and the moments of inertia are important variables in determining the thermodynamic functions of a molecule.

The total partition function can be expressed as the product of the individual partition functions due to translational, rotational, vibrational and electronic energies. Hence,

$$Q = Q_{\text{trans}} \cdot Q_{\text{rot}} \cdot Q_{\text{vib}} \cdot Q_{\text{elec}} \\ = \sum_i g_i \exp(-\epsilon_i/kT) \quad (1)$$

where, g_i is the statistical weight of the i th energy level¹², k is the Boltzmann constant and T is the absolute temperature. Contribution of each partition function may be evaluated separately and then added to the corresponding thermodynamic function to obtain the total values. The electronic contribution is small and is ignored because ϵ_{elec} is large compared to kT at ordinary temperature. The equations used in computation for various partition functions and their contribution to different thermodynamic parameters are given elsewhere¹³. The standard expressions¹³ as given by Colthup have been used and their contributions to various thermodynamic functions have been calculated at various temperatures. In the present work, computations of the thermodynamic quantities were made on a TDC-316 Computer.

Results and Discussion

The statistical mechanical calculation of the ideal gas thermodynamic properties for a molecule requires the following basic informations: atomic masses, molecular weights, molecular structural parameters, complete fundamental vibrational frequencies (3N-6) and the symmetry number.

The molecular structures of pyrimidine, 2-chloropyrimidine, 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine and 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine are taken from literature^{10,14} and are used as such in the calculations. The atomic masses are taken from literature¹⁵: C, 12.011 15; H, 1.007 97; N, 14.006 7; F, 18.998 4; Cl 35.453. All the four molecules have been considered to have C_{2v} symmetry with their external symmetry number σ equal to 2. In the computation of principal moments of inertia I_x , I_y and I_z , all the molecules have been considered as planar and the Z-axis perpendicular to the plane. The fundamental frequencies of pyrimidine, 2-chloropyrimidine, 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine and 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine are assigned in references^{7,9-11} to the various modes of vibration. The computed results¹⁶ of the thermodynamic functions, namely, the heat capacity (C_p°) at constant pressure, the enthalpy function ($H^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T , the free energy function ($G^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T